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Resolving the importance of dense shelf water transport for cross-shelf exchange

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Abstract

Quantifying cross-shelf water exchange from the coastal to the open ocean is considered one of the main challenges in coastal physical oceanography. Cross-shelf water exchange is important for the net transport of oxygen, nutrients, sediment, and organic material across the continental shelf and affects marine ecosystems and biogeochemical cycles. Dense shelf water transport (DSWT) is a cross-shelf exchange mechanism where dense water forms along the coastline (through cooling or evaporation) and then flows along the seafloor across the continental shelf. DSWT occurs at a regional scale in many mid-latitude locations with a Mediterranean climate. Along the Australian continent, DSWT typically extends to the shelf break and occurs along the entire continental shelf. In this study, we developed an algorithm to detect DSWT in a 3D numerical ocean model, which we applied to an area in south-western Australia to analyze DSWT from 2000 until 2023. We found that DSWT consistently occurred in colder months, with large interannual variability and higher DSWT during La Niña years. Overall, the mean cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT across the 50 m bathymetry contour was $0.02 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, which would result in 0.68 Sv ($1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$) over the entire Australian continental shelf. Compared to existing global estimates of cross-shelf DSWT of 3 Sv , this suggests that DSWT along Australia may be globally significant. It is likely that similar transport occurs along many mid-latitude continental shelves, and DSWT may be a globally overlooked phenomenon contributing to cross-shelf exchange and global biogeochemical cycles.

Significance statement

The exchange of water between shallow coastal regions and the deeper ocean is an important driver of marine ecosystem structure and function. While various physical mechanisms drive this exchange, water movement across the coastline is typically much weaker than along it, making “cross-shelf transport” challenging to study. Here, we focused on a specific mechanism that leads to cross-shelf transport of dense, cold, oxygen- and carbon-enriched, water along the seafloor away from the coastal ocean. We consistently detected this transport in a 3D ocean model off south-western Australia. Its regular occurrence and water properties suggest it may play a significant role in cross-shelf transport around Australia, with potential global implications for marine ecosystem dynamics and biogeochemical cycles.

1 Introduction

Cross-shelf water exchange is considered one of the main challenges in coastal physical oceanography (Brink, 2016) and is a key pathway through which nutrients, materials, and organisms are introduced or removed from the continental shelf. This exchange is central in determining biogeochemical cycles, can alter ocean temperature and salinity, drive carbon fluxes and phytoplankton blooms, and structure coastal, shelf, and deep-sea ecosystems (e.g. Holt et al., 2009; Luna et al., 2016; Laruelle et al., 2018; Dai et al., 2022; Moulton et al., 2023; Filbee-Dexter et al., 2024). However, cross-shelf currents are typically weak flows that are often overshadowed by much stronger—and typically better studied and more predictable—along-shelf currents (e.g. Allen, 1980). The weaker nature of cross-shelf flows, combined with the many processes that can generate them, makes them challenging to identify and predict.

Different processes drive cross-shelf transport on the continental shelf. These processes depend on the shelf location and can include: wind stress, both through Ekman transport as well as direct cross-shelf transport on the shallower inner shelf; surface gravity waves (e.g. Stokes drift); tides; (mesoscale and sub-mesoscale) eddies; buoyant plumes from fresh river outflows; and dense water transport (e.g. Lentz and Fewings, 2012; Brink, 2016; Mahjabin et al., 2020). Dense water transport typically results in rates of cross-shelf flows of comparable magnitude to other mechanisms, however it is notable because the water that is exported from the shelf and along the seafloor is dense, oxygenated, and contains organic matter (e.g. Shapiro et al., 2003; Sanchez-Vidal et al., 2008; Pattiaratchi et al., 2017). When this dense shelf water is transported to the shelf edge it can “cascade” off the shelf and contribute to the formation of intermediate and deep waters (e.g. Shapiro et al., 2003). The export of dense, oxygenated, water leads to ventilation of deep water masses (e.g. Coppola et al., 2017; Rhein et al., 2017), which can substantially affect deep-sea ecosystems (e.g. Luna et al., 2016). Dense water formation is also important for the uptake of anthropogenic carbon (e.g. Rhein et al., 2017) and is an important driver of the “continental shelf carbon pump” (Tsugonai et al., 1999). Large-scale dense shelf water flows in the Antarctic contribute to the global thermohaline circulation and formation of Antarctic Bottom Water (e.g. Baines and Condie, 1998; Li et al., 2023). However, smaller scale dense shelf water transport and cascades occur in many other locations around the world (Figure 1a; e.g. Ivanov et al., 2004), and may be important regional drivers of cross-shelf exchange.

Dense shelf water cascades occur in several locations in the Arctic (Luneva et al., 2020) as well as in many mid-latitude locations with a Mediterranean climate (high evaporation, low precipitation and freshwater river input; e.g. Ivanov et al., 2004). In mid-latitude locations, dense shelf water transport has most extensively been studied in the Mediterranean Sea (e.g. Canals et al., 2006; Ulses et al., 2008; Mihanović et al., 2013) and on the Australian continental shelf (e.g. Shearman and Brink, 2010; Pattiaratchi et al., 2011; Mahjabin et al., 2019a,b, 2020). In the Mediterranean Sea, dense shelf water cascades occur in specific locations (e.g. Gulf of Lion, Adriatic Sea) and under extreme conditions can reach depths >1000 m. In contrast, around Australia, dense shelf water transport occurs along the entire continental shelf, typically reaching depths between 80 to 150 m (Mahjabin et al., 2020) and rarely “cascading” off the shelf edge. On the Australian shelf, following van der Mheen et al. (2024), we therefore refer to the more general “dense shelf water transport” (DSWT) rather than cascades.

Despite typically reaching shallower depths than in other regions around the world, DSWT on the Australian continental shelf still results in substantial cross-shelf water transport and exchange of temperature, salinity, oxygen, organic material, and sediment (Figures 1f, g, h). Even without cascading off the shelf edge, DSWT has been shown to initiate transport of organic material past the continental shelf edge to depths >200 m (van der Mheen et al., 2024) and is an important mechanism connecting the continental shelf to deep waters. In addition, DSWT along Australia seems unique because it occurs along the entire continent (Mahjabin et al., 2020), the coastline of which spans over 28000 km (Geoscience Australia, 2009). As a result, the overall cross-shelf transport due to DSWT along Australia may be highly significant.

DSWT is challenging to observe, both because of its intermittent nature (Ivanov et al., 2004) and because it occurs along the seafloor, making it impossible to observe with satellites. It is also challenging to identify in single profiles, instead requiring observations along a transect. Although ocean gliders enable

regular sampling of transects at high resolution (e.g. Pattiaratchi et al., 2011), and DSWT can be easily recognized as a wedge of dense water protruding under lighter water in these transects (Figure 1c), these observations are still limited to specific locations. Because of these challenges, DSWT is mostly observed in specific regions where it was already known to occur. Being able to detect DSWT in numerical ocean models is therefore important to allow large-scale analyses of DSWT, to quantify the resulting cross-shelf transport, as well as to identify new regions where DSWT might occur.

In this study, we therefore developed an algorithm for automated detection of DSWT on the continental shelf and applied it to a long-term (24 years) 3D numerical ocean model simulation of continental shelf and slope processes along the Wadjemup (Rottne) Continental Shelf (WCS) in south-west Australia (Figure 1b). We determined the occurrence, cross-shelf transport, and flow patterns of DSWT and their seasonal and inter-annual variability from 2000 to 2023.

Figure 1: (a) Approximate locations of observed dense shelf water transport (DSWT) around the world, based on Ivanov et al. (2004), Mahjabin (2019), Mahjabin et al. (2020), Luneva et al. (2020), and references therein. (b) Overview of the Wadjemup (Rottne) Continental Shelf (WCS), showing the main topographical and oceanographic features. The inset map in panel a shows Western Australia (black box in panel a) with the WCS indicated by the thick black box. Background colors and contours show the bathymetry based on data from Geoscience Australia (2009). The southwards flowing Leeuwin Current (LC) and seasonal northwards flowing Capes Current (CC) are shown schematically with red and blue arrows respectively. Ocean glider measurements along the “Two Rocks” transect (black dots in panel b) from the 30th of June until the 2nd of July 2022 during a DSWT event, showing: (c) seawater density (as σ_T , the density-1000 kg m^{-3}), calculated based on the measured temperature, salinity, and depth (pressure); (d) ocean temperature; (e) salinity; (f) dissolved oxygen; (g) colored dissolved organic matter (in equivalent mass fraction of quinine sulfate dihydrate); and (h) particle backscatter, which is a proxy for suspended matter that can be both inorganic (sediment) or organic. These observations along the transect illustrate what a typical DSWT event on the WCS looks like (a wedge of dense, cold water below lighter, warmer water; with salinity usually not playing a role) and how these events lead to cross-shelf transport of important physical, chemical, and biological properties and matter.

1.1 Wadjemup (Rottnest) Continental Shelf

We examined DSWT along the WCS in south-western Australia (inset map in Figure 1a). In this region, the continental shelf slopes gently downwards to 50 m depth and then rapidly increases in depth until the shelf edge at 200 m. The WCS is relatively wide and extends approximately 40 to 50 km offshore before reaching 50 m depth. A shallow region extends between Perth and Wadjemup (Rottnest Island, 20 km west of Perth; Figure 1b), which interrupts the along-shore flow. The Perth Canyon (Trotter et al., 2019), approximately 20 km west of Wadjemup, drops to depths >6000 m (the 1000 m bathymetry contour at the head of the canyon is shown in Figure 1b).

The WCS experiences a Mediterranean climate, with approximately 2.5 m annual mean evaporation and 730 mm precipitation (Mahjabin et al., 2019b). The Leeuwin Current (LC) is the main boundary current along Western Australia and flows polewards (opposite to the direction expected from Sverdrup theory, Figure 1b; e.g. Pattiaratchi and Woo, 2009; Wijeratne et al., 2018). The LC is characterized by warm, low salinity water. During warmer months (October to March), Western Australia experiences some of the strongest seabreezes in the world (Masselink and Pattiaratchi, 2001; Rafiq et al., 2020), resulting in southerly winds >15 m s⁻¹ during the afternoon. These strong southerly winds weaken the LC and drive the seasonal Capes Current (CC), which flows northwards inshore of the LC (Figure 1b; Pearce and Pattiaratchi, 1999; Bitencourt et al., 2024).

DSWT formation can occur when there is a negative horizontal density gradient (increasing density towards the coast) because of higher salinity and/or colder water along the coast. Along the Australian continental shelf, negative density gradients are mainly temperature driven (Mahjabin et al., 2020). The dense water formed along the coast descends and flows across the continental shelf along the seafloor, as a density-driven gravity current. DSWT is recognizable in cross-shelf transects as a wedge of denser water protruding under lighter water on the continental shelf (see Figures 1c, d, and e for an example DSWT event on the WCS driven by a temperature gradient). In addition to a negative horizontal density gradient, the water column needs to be stratified for DSWT to occur (except for the “formation region” along the coast; e.g. Mahjabin et al., 2020; Luneva et al., 2020). As a result, the formation of DSWT can be disrupted by mixing due to tides and wind. The WCS is a microtidal region, with a tidal range of only 0.5 m, and therefore disruption of DSWT because of tidal mixing is negligible (Mahjabin et al., 2019a,b). Mixing due to strong winds can disrupt DSWT formation on the WCS, depending on both the wind speed and direction. Offshore winds and transport results in vertical mixing due to dense water flowing over less dense water, which disrupts DSWT formation. In contrast, onshore winter storms with conditions favorable to downwelling can lead to enhancement of DSWT rather than disruption (Wu et al., 2018; Mahjabin et al., 2019a,b).

During warmer months on the WCS, there is saline and warm water along the coast, which typically results in a weak but positive horizontal density gradient (decreasing densities towards the coast) of $<2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg m⁻⁴ (van der Mheen et al., 2024). The presence of strong sea breezes also results in strong vertical mixing of the water column (Pattiaratchi et al., 2011). As a result, DSWT is usually limited during warmer months. During colder months, differential cooling leads to negative horizontal density gradients reaching $<-2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$ kg m⁻⁴. As a result, DSWT frequently occurs on the WCS during colder months, typically peaking around June (e.g. Mahjabin et al., 2020; van der Mheen et al., 2024).

2 Methods

We developed an algorithm to automatically detect DSWT in a 3D numerical ocean model and estimate associated cross-shelf transport. We applied this algorithm to a regional ocean model on the WCS. In the following subsections we describe: the regional ocean model that we used to analyze DSWT on the WCS (section 22.1); the algorithm to detect DSWT and estimate cross-shelf transport (section 22.2); and calculations of surface buoyancy fluxes (section 22.3), which we used to validate the DSWT detection algorithm as well to help explain the interannual variability of DSWT on the WCS.

2.1 Ocean circulation model (CWA-ROMS)

CWA-ROMS is a high-resolution set-up of the Regional Ocean Modelling System (ROMS, Haidvogel et al., 2008) of the central west coast of Australia (CWA). CWA-ROMS outputs every 3 hours, has a horizontal resolution of 1.7 to 2.1 km on a curvilinear grid, and has 25 vertical sigma (terrain-following) layers. On the continental shelf (<200 m depth), the bottom layer thickness is typically between <1 and 10 m. We used data from 2000 until 2023, for which CWA-ROMS was run in reanalysis mode. Ocean boundary and initial conditions were provided by the operational analysis and forecast system of Mercator Ocean International with 1/12° horizontal resolution. Atmospheric forcing was provided by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ERA-5 model output at 25 km horizontal resolution and hourly temporal resolution. Tidal forcing was provided by the TPXO9 global tidal solution (Egbert and Erofeeva, 2002).

In this study, we analyzed DSWT in the region of CWA-ROMS between 114-116°E and 31-33°S, which we refer to as the WCS. CWA-ROMS can DSWT: van der Mheen et al. (2024) used CWA-ROMS to simulate the transport of particulate organic material (kelp detritus) by DSWT, and Mahjabin et al. (2019b) compared simulated DSWT from a model nested in CWA-ROMS with DSWT events measured by ocean gliders.

We used the following data fields from CWA-ROMS for different purposes: bathymetry data to generate cross-shelf transects (section 22.2); temperature and salinity fields to calculate water densities to detect DSWT (section 22.2); u - and v -velocity fields to estimate cross-shelf transport (section 22.2); and net surface heat- and salt fluxes to calculate buoyancy fluxes (section 22.3). We also used ECMWF ERA-5 data to determine wind speed anomalies and wind directions, which we used to help explain the interannual variability of DSWT on the WCS.

2.2 Dense shelf water transport detection

We used an algorithm to detect DSWT along transects in CWA-ROMS from 2000 until 2023 and estimated the cross-shelf transport due to DSWT. Although we applied our algorithm to CWA-ROMS and analyzed the cross-shelf transport along the WCS, the algorithm can be used in other locations using similar 3D ocean models. Our (Python) code to detect DSWT is available on https://github.com/mheen/dswt_detector. We describe the exact steps taken to detect DSWT in the following sections.

2.2.1 Cross-shelf transects

We detected DSWT in cross-shelf transects that run approximately perpendicular to the depth contours, using bathymetry data from CWA-ROMS. Detecting DSWT in cross-slope transects is common practice and is justified by the strong stabilizing effect of friction in the bottom layer, which enables an ageostrophic down-slope flow (Ivanov et al., 2004). In addition, for the WCS, our focus is predominantly in relatively shallow water ~ 50 m depth, which is shallower than the Ekman depth of ~ 70 m in this region (Mihanovic et al., 2016; Chen et al., 2019). As a result, Coriolis effects are minimal over the depth range that we are interested in (Lentz and Fewings, 2012). We determined these transects semi-automatically in several steps.

First, our algorithm determined evenly spaced starting points along a shallow bathymetry contour (10 m on the WCS), where the points were spaced at approximately the size of a grid cell in CWA-ROMS (~ 2 km). At each point the angle perpendicular to the contour, and where this perpendicular line intersected with the next bathymetry contour was then determined. From this point, the perpendicular angle and the intersecting point on the following contour was again determined. If the difference between perpendicular angles from one contour line to the next was larger than 45° , the average between these two angles was used to prevent extremely sharp direction changes in a transect. This process was repeated along the bathymetry contours $b = \{10, 20, \dots, 100, 120, \dots, 200\}$ m.

After automatically generating transects, we manually removed any that looked faulty. These were typically transects that crossed others. Subsequently, our code allows transects in specific areas and starting from a different bathymetry contour to be added back in, which can be useful around islands. On the WCS, we added transects starting from the 40 m contour to the west of Wadjemup.

The resulting transects on the WCS are shown in Figure 2a. Our aim was to determine cross-shelf transects that do not cross each other and that cover the WCS as fully as possible (minimal gaps in Figure 2b). We avoided transects that crossed others because in later steps we determined the cross-shelf transport by calculating the down-transect velocities, which would not be consistent in crossing transects. Overlapping transects (yellow areas in Figure 2b) because of local deep areas were deemed acceptable.

We extracted CWA-ROMS data from grid cells on each transect and used this data to detect DSWT and to estimate the cross-shelf transport, as described in the following subsections.

Figure 2: Cross-shelf transect determination on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS). (a) Transects (in red) on the WCS in CWA-ROMS, which are used to detect DSWT and to determine cross-shelf transport. Transects should be approximately perpendicular to the bathymetry contours (shown in black at {10, 20, ...100, 120, ...200} m) and not cross each other. (b) Number of times that CWA-ROMS grid cells are included in a transect.

2.2.2 Dense shelf water transport detection and performance

For each cross-shelf transect, we determined if there was DSWT based on two conditions:

1. There must be a negative horizontal density gradient along the transect (i.e. higher density along the coast). We determined this by calculating the depth mean density $\bar{\rho}$ and then determining if the mean over the entire transect $\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial x} < 0$.
2. The vertical density gradient $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ in the bottom layers must exceed a certain minimum value for a minimum amount of consecutive grid cells. Because DSWT is characterized by a wedge of dense water below less dense water, this can be observed as a sudden jump in the vertical density gradient $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ (Figure 3d). The exact value that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ needs to exceed depends on the study region and the ocean model, and needs to be determined manually. For the WCS in CWA-ROMS we set $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$, which is a typical threshold value that we observed in transects when DSWT occurred. This condition needed to hold for 30% of consecutive grid cells along the transect. The condition for a minimum amount of consecutive grid cells exceeding the threshold $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ value was added to ensure that there is substantial DSWT along the transect. Sudden changes in $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ also occurred at the ocean surface (for example Figure S1, during high evaporation). To prevent these events from being detected as DSWT, we also set the condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$ in the bottom 30% of grid cells.

When both conditions held, we determined that there was DSWT in a transect.

We checked the performance of our algorithm by showing density, temperature, and salinity plots along 1030 random transects during 2017, concentrated around months when DSWT occurs frequently (Figure S2a), and visually determining if there was DSWT. We compared this to what our algorithm determined. The algorithm had a high accuracy of 91.7% (46.5% false positives and 53.5% false negatives, Figure S2b). Most cases where there was a disagreement between our algorithm and our visual inspection were doubtful cases that were difficult to determine visually. We also compared the results of the DSWT detection algorithm in a single transect with the surface buoyancy flux along the coastline during 2017 (Figure 4; see section 2.2.3 for the method used to calculate the surface buoyancy flux). In 82% of the cases when DSWT was detected there was also a negative surface buoyancy flux along the coastline. Since this is the main formation mechanism of DSWT, this gives us further confidence in our DSWT detection algorithm.

For each transect on the WCS we determined if there was DSWT at 3-hourly intervals and calculated a daily fraction of DSWT in each transect. To determine the overall occurrence of DSWT on the WCS, we calculated the daily, monthly, or yearly fraction of DSWT over all transects (defined as the “DSWT occurrence”).

Figure 3: Water properties along a transect in CWA-ROMS on the 1st of June 2017 at 12:00 UTC. During this time and along this transect there was dense shelf water transport (DSWT), which is characterized by denser (in this case both colder and more saline) water along the coastline and a wedge of dense water protruding under less dense surface water. The transect location is shown by the red line in the map inset in panel a. The water (a) temperature, (b) salinity, and (c) density are shown, as well as the (d) vertical density gradient $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$, which our algorithm uses to detect DSWT.

Figure 4: Dense shelf water transport (DSWT) detection and buoyancy fluxes along a single transect (red line in the inset map in panel c) on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS) for 2017. **(a)** Surface heat and salt fluxes along the coastline in the selected transect (black cross in the inset map in panel c). A negative heat flux indicates cooling at the ocean surface; a negative salt flux indicates a net freshening at the ocean surface. **(b)** Net surface buoyancy flux along the coastline in the transect, where a negative buoyancy flux indicates increasing water density at the surface. **(c)** DSWT occurrence in the transect as detected by the algorithm. Blue shading indicates times when there was a negative surface buoyancy flux. In 82% of the cases where DSWT was detected, there was also a negative buoyancy flux.

2.2.3 Cross-shelf transport calculation

To determine the cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT, our goal was to calculate the cross-shelf transport in grid cells where DSWT was detected, as well as over the relevant depth range in which there was DSWT. We did this by first calculating the down-transect velocity for each transect in which there was DSWT. In each grid location along the transect where $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{m}^{-1}$, we determined the cross-shelf transport in the depth layers below which the $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ condition was first exceeded. We did this by multiplying the down-transect velocity in each grid cell by its thickness at 3-hourly intervals and summed values in the same location to get the depth-integrated daily transport in m^2 for each location along a transect. As an example, Figure 5 shows the grid cells along a transect that were used to calculate the cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT along that transect. In grid cells that were in multiple transects (Figure 2b), we took the mean cross-shelf transport to determine the overall transport associated with DSWT. We show our results as transport maps, but also calculated the total cross-shelf transport across the 50 m bathymetry contour to show as timeseries.

As a confidence check, we compared the cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT across the 50 m bathymetry contour as calculated by the algorithm (using the method described above) with a simplified, but more direct cross-shelf transport calculation. For this, we determined the transport perpendicular to the 50 m bathymetry contour over a fixed number of bottom layers (we used 1, 2, and 3 layers) in CWA-ROMS during times and in locations where DSWT was detected. The main difference between this method and that used by the algorithm, is that the algorithm determines over how many bottom layers it should calculate the DSWT-associated transport, rather than taking a fixed amount of layers. If the cross-shelf transects are not strictly perpendicular to the 50 m bathymetry contour, this may also result in differences between the two methods (since the algorithm calculates cross-shelf transport in the down-transect direction, rather than perpendicular to a specific depth contour). We found that the cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT as calculated by the algorithm agreed well with cross-shelf transport perpendicular to the 50 m bathymetry contour over the bottom 3 layers in CWA-ROMS (Figure S4a), giving us confidence in the cross-shelf transport estimated by our algorithm.

In some scenarios, DSWT was wrongly detected by the algorithm. We removed cross-shelf transport associated with three of these scenarios: (1) negative cross-shelf transport (towards the coast) as this is not associated with DSWT (Luneva et al. (2020) used a similar approach) but with other dense water flows along the seafloor (see for example Figure S5); (2) cross-shelf transport that only occurred along depths >45 m in transects—although this transport may be associated with dense water transport off the continental shelf, because it was not formed in shallower water along the coast, we do not consider it DSWT—(see for example Figure S6); and (3) wrongly detected DSWT in transects to the west of Wadjemup, for which we removed any cross-shelf transport if no DSWT was detected in any other transects along the WCS (see for example Figure S7). Although the effect of these erroneously detected cases was negligible on the DSWT occurrence and minimal on the cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT, we acknowledge that these are limitations of our algorithm.

Figure 5: Illustration of the method we used to determine the cross-shelf transport associated with dense shelf water transport (DSWT) using a transect in CWA-ROMS on the 1st of June 2017 at 12:00 UTC, during which time there was DSWT. The transect location is shown by the red line in the map inset in panel a. (a) Water density along the transect, as in Figure 3c. (b) Down-transect velocity along the transect, with positive values indicating velocities directed offshore. The red boxes in both panels show the grid cells that were used to calculate the cross-shelf transport.

2.2.4 Dense shelf water transport events

The occurrence of DSWT increases during colder months on the WCS, when $\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial x} < 0$ (Mahjabin et al., 2020; van der Mheen et al., 2024). However, the formation of DSWT is typically also disrupted by wind mixing on timescales of a few days (Mahjabin et al., 2019a). We defined DSWT “events” as peaks in DSWT occurrence (see Figure S8 for defined events in 2017), as an indication of how often DSWT forms and is disrupted each year. We also used this definition to determine typical event durations, as well properties such as cross-shelf velocities and thickness of the DSWT layer.

2.2.5 Other dense shelf water transport detection methods

Other methods have previously been used to determine if conditions are suitable for DSWT formation. These methods mainly considered different ways to determine if stratifying or mixing effects were dominant during specific conditions. For example, Mahjabin et al. (2020) used the Richardson or Simpson number Ri_x (Simpson et al., 2005; Burchard, 2009) to determine whether stratification due to horizontal density gradients dominated over mixing, when:

$$Ri_x = \frac{g}{\rho} \frac{h^2}{u_{*wt}^2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} > \mathcal{O}(1), \quad (1)$$

where g is the gravitational acceleration, ρ is the water density, $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x}$ the horizontal density gradient, h the water depth, and u_{*wt} is the combined effect of wind and tidal stress.

A similar method, for example used by Hetzel et al. (2013), is to determine whether

$$\underbrace{\frac{1}{320} \frac{g^2 h^4}{\rho K_{mz}} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} \right)^2}_{\text{gravitational}} > \underbrace{\frac{4\epsilon \kappa_D \rho}{3\pi} \frac{u_b^3}{h}}_{\text{tidal mixing}} + \underbrace{\delta \kappa_s \rho_a \frac{W^3}{h}}_{\text{wind mixing}}, \quad (2)$$

where K_{mz} is the vertical eddy diffusivity, ϵ the tidal mixing efficiency, κ_D the drag coefficient, u_b the bottom tidal velocity, δ the wind mixing efficiency, ρ_a the air density and W the wind speed.

As a variation on these methods, van der Mheen et al. (2024) combined the condition $\frac{\partial \bar{\rho}}{\partial x} < 0$, equations 2 and $\phi > 5$ (where ϕ is the potential energy anomaly, a measure for water column stratification, see equation 7 in section 22.3) with a condition for wind direction (where onshore wind was still suitable for DSWT, as determined by Mahjabin et al., 2019a,b) to determine if conditions were suitable for DSWT formation.

However, both the Richardson number in equation 1 and the balance between the gravitational circulation and mixing effects in equation 2 were originally determined for estuaries and do not always work well when applied over the entire continental shelf. For example, the Richardson number can become quite large with larger water depths h and the condition $Ri_x > \mathcal{O}(1)$ for DSWT may no longer be valid.

Cross-shelf velocities associated with DSWT have previously been determined using the Nof velocity v_N (Nof, 1983; Shapiro et al., 2003; Ivanov et al., 2004; Luneva et al., 2020). Here, the cross-shelf velocity v_c is calculated as $v_c \approx 0.2v_N$, where the Nof velocity v_N is the along-shelf velocity (geostrophic component of the flow) given by

$$v_N = g \frac{\bar{\rho}_s - \bar{\rho}_a}{\bar{\rho}_a} \frac{\bar{s}}{f}, \quad (3)$$

where $\bar{\rho}_s$ is the average density in the DSWT plume, $\bar{\rho}_a$ is the average density of the ambient water, \bar{s} is the average slope, and f is the Coriolis parameter.

However, idealized numerical models (Shapiro and Hill, 1997) based on laboratory experiments (Shapiro and Zatsepin, 1997) were used to determine $v_c \approx 0.2v_N$, and can be off by a factor of 10-30 from real-world scenarios (Luneva et al., 2020). In addition, because we consider DSWT on smaller scales and in relatively shallow water on the WCS, the Nof velocity may not be relevant in this case, since Coriolis effects are expected to be minimal and there may not be a significant geostrophic flow component related to DSWT.

Despite room for future improvement, we are confident in the DSWT detection algorithm and its performance. Our results of monthly mean DSWT occurrence on the WCS in 2017 agree well with those of van der Mheen et al. (2024, Figure S3), and the values we find for cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT agree well with those from previous observations and modeling studies on the WCS (Mahjabin et al., 2019a,b, see also section 4).

2.3 Buoyancy fluxes and stratification

For DSWT to form, there needs to be a negative surface buoyancy flux along the coast, forming dense water (e.g. Gawarkiewicz and Chapman, 1995), and the water column needs to be stratified. We calculated the buoyancy flux (as described in the following paragraphs) up to 30 m depth along a single transect for a direct comparison with the DSWT detection algorithm (see section 22.2). We also calculated the buoyancy flux up to 30 m depth and the potential energy anomaly (PEA; as described below) as a measure of water column stratification up to 50 m depth on the WCS to help explain interannual variability of DSWT formation.

Following e.g. Fairall et al. (2003), we determine the buoyancy flux B as:

$$B = B_h + B_w, \quad (4)$$

where

$$B_h = \alpha \frac{Q_{net}}{C_p} \quad (5)$$

is the surface buoyancy flux, α is the coefficient of thermal expansion given in Table A3.1 in Gill (1982), $C_p = 4000 \text{ J kg}^{-1}\text{K}^{-1}$ is the specific heat of sea water, and Q_{net} is the net surface heat flux, obtained from CWA-ROMS. The surface buoyancy salt flux B_w is given by

$$B_w = \beta \rho S(P - E)$$

where β is the haline contraction coefficient, ρ is the water density, S the surface salinity, P the precipitation and E the evaporation at the ocean surface. Since $\beta = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial S}$, and CWA-ROMS returns the net surface salt flux $F_{S,net} = S(E - P)$, this can be simplified to

$$B_w = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial S} F_{S,net}, \quad (6)$$

where $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial S}$ is given in Table A3.1 in Gill (1982). For DSWT formation on the WCS, the buoyancy heat flux typically dominates over the buoyancy salt flux. We used the surface buoyancy flux B to validate the DSWT detection algorithm along a single transect (see section 22.2). We also used the monthly mean surface buoyancy flux along the entire WCS up to 30 m depth to help explain the interannual variability of DSWT.

Mixing can disrupt the formation of DSWT. The PEA ϕ can be used as a measure to determine how well-mixed or stratified the water column is (e.g. Simpson, 1981), where

$$\phi = \frac{1}{h} \int_{-h}^0 (\bar{\rho} - \rho) g z dz. \quad (7)$$

Here, h is the water depth, $\bar{\rho}$ is the depth-mean density and g is the gravitational acceleration. Theoretically, values of $\phi = 0$ indicate that the water column is fully mixed; increasing values of ϕ indicate a more strongly stratified water column. We used monthly mean anomalies of PEA to try and help explain the interannual variability of DSWT on the WCS.

3 Results

3.1 Dense shelf water transport on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf

From 2000 until 2023, DSWT was a consistently occurring phenomenon that led to cross-shelf transport on the WCS. DSWT predominantly occurred during the colder months, typically peaking during June at $>60\%$ (Figure 6a). Cross-shelf transport because of DSWT also peaked in June, with monthly mean transport $>0.1 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$ across the 50 m bathymetry contour (Figure 6b). During June, DSWT explained $\sim 70\%$ of the overall monthly mean cross-shelf transport along the seafloor (Figure S4b). In most years, there was no DSWT during the warmer months. Both DSWT occurrence and associated cross-shelf transport are strongly correlated to the monthly mean net surface buoyancy flux along the coast on the WCS (Figure 6c), with linear Pearson correlation coefficients of $R = -0.91$ and $R = -0.82$ (p -values $\ll 0.01$) respectively.

On average, there were 40 DSWT “events” per year, which lasted ~ 5 days (Figure S9). Mean cross-shelf velocities associated with DSWT were around 0.05 m s^{-1} with maximum velocities $>0.2 \text{ m s}^{-1}$. The average thickness of DSWT during these events was $\sim 6 \text{ m}$, with maximum thicknesses of 27 m . DSWT on average reached depths of 40 m along the shelf and maximum depths of $\sim 150 \text{ m}$.

DSWT did not occur evenly across the WCS but varied spatially (Figure 6d). The largest offshore transport generally occurred in two locations north of Wadjemup, with mean transport values of around $0.8 \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. During typical conditions in the colder months, there was southwards advection along the coast due to the Leeuwin Current (LC). This flow moved south-westwards when encountering shallower water around Wadjemup, which also concentrated the cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT directly north-west of Wadjemup (see Figure 7 for an example event illustrating this effect and Video S1 for an animation of the full year 2017). A similar effect occurred further north around 31.5°S , where ocean currents were also deflected south-westwards by the bathymetry.

Figure 6: Dense shelf water transport (DSWT) from 2000 until 2023 on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf. **(a)** Monthly mean occurrence of DSWT over all transects. **(b)** Monthly mean cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT across the 50 m bathymetry contour (highlighted with a thick black line in panel d). Black crosses in panels a and b show yearly mean values. **(c)** Monthly mean net surface buoyancy flux along the coast (up to depth of 30 m). A negative buoyancy flux indicates the formation of denser water at the ocean surface. The linear Pearson correlation coefficient R between monthly DSWT occurrence and buoyancy flux is $R = -0.91$ (p -value $\ll 0.01$) and between associated cross-shelf transport and buoyancy flux is $R = -0.82$ (p -value $\ll 0.01$). **(d)** Map showing the mean cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT up to 100 m depth over the entire time period on the WCS.

Figure 7: Example dense shelf water transport (DSWT) event on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS) during 2017. The colormap indicates cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT as detected by our algorithm. Black arrows show daily mean bottom ocean current velocities from CWA-ROMS. The thick light blue arrow indicates the daily mean wind direction over the WCS based on ECMWF ERA-5 data, with the mean wind speed in m s^{-1} shown inside the arrow. Bathymetry contours at 25, 50, 100, and 200 m are shown by black lines, with the 50 m contour highlighted by a tick line. Daily mean maps for: (a) 31 May 2017, (b) 1 June 2017, (c) 2 June 2017, (d) 3 June 2017, (e) 4 June 2017, and (f) 5 June 2017.

3.2 Interannual variability of dense shelf water transport

Although DSWT occurred consistently throughout 2000 until 2023 and peaked during the colder months, there was strong interannual variability in both DSWT occurrence (Figure 8a) and cross-shelf transport on the WCS (Figure 8b). Relative annual anomalies reached $\sim 25\%$ for DSWT occurrence and up to 50% for cross-shelf transport.

DSWT occurrence appeared to increase with the strength of the LC, for which the mean sea level at Fremantle is a proxy (Figure 8c; Bitencourt et al., 2024). The strength of the LC is related to the El Niño Southern Oscillation (e.g. Wolter and Timlin, 2011), and is higher during La Niña years (Figure 8c; Pattiaratchi and Buchan, 1991; Feng et al., 2003, 2009; Wijeratne et al., 2018; Bitencourt et al., 2024). Indeed, DSWT typically occurred more frequently on the WCS during La Niña years (2008, 2010, 2011, 2022; Figure 8a). During these years, wind speeds were typically lower than average and in warmer months were more south-easterly rather than southerly (Figure S9b; Bitencourt et al., 2024). Although this may have resulted in less wind mixing and more stratified water columns, this was not reflected in the monthly mean PEA anomalies during these years (Figure S9c). Both inshore (up to 30 m depth) and further offshore (between 50 and 300 m depth) there was larger than normal surface cooling (negative heat flux anomalies in Figures S10b and S11b), resulting in overall negative surface buoyancy flux anomalies (Figures S10d and S11d). The relatively higher sea surface temperatures and lower salinities during the warmer months in these years are associated with a stronger LC (Figures S10c and S11c).

Since 2015 was the only year with a strong and year-round El Niño event in our data set, and its effects were not clearly opposite to those of La Niña years, we were not able to determine the effect of El Niño years on DSWT occurrence. However, during years with a weaker than normal LC (e.g. 2002 to 2005) DSWT typically occurred less frequently and were associated with less than average cross-shelf transport (Figure 8).

Years that experienced higher-than-average occurrence of DSWT also experienced larger transport across the 50 m bathymetry contour (Figure 8b). However, the timing of when most transport occurred varied per year (black line in Figure 8b). For example, in 2011, there was unseasonal DSWT over the entire WCS during February and March, but less than the mean transport during the colder months (Figures S13 and S14). In contrast, in 2022 there was negligible DSWT during February and March but strong transport during June and July continuing above average into August (Figures S15 and S16).

Although both the Indian Ocean Dipole (Saji et al., 1999) and the Southern Annual Mode (Gong and Wang, 1999) are known to affect the strength of westerly winds and storm events during the colder months (Feng et al., 2009), it is difficult to determine the effect of these climate modes on monthly oceanic variations on the WCS (Wandres et al., 2017) and we did not find an obvious relationship between them and the occurrence of DSWT.

3.3 Overall cross-shelf dense shelf water transport

Across the 50 m bathymetry contour on the WCS, DSWT resulted in mean cross-shelf transport of $0.02 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$. This amounts to a total cross-shelf transport of $6460 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$ or 0.006 Sv ($1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$) over the entire WCS (using the length of the 50 m bathymetry contour of 267 km). This translates to 0.002 Sv per 100 km of shelf. Assuming that similar transport values are valid along the entire Australian coastline, this would result in an average cross-shelf transport of 0.68 Sv associated with DSWT for all of Australia (assuming a shelf length of 28000 km based on data from Geoscience Australia, 2009).

Figure 8: Interannual variability of dense shelf water transport (DSWT) on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS). **(a)** DSWT yearly mean occurrence anomaly. **(b)** DSWT yearly mean cross-shelf transport anomaly along the 50 m depth contour. **(c)** Monthly El Niño Southern Oscillation indicator, using the Multivariate ENSO Index v2 (Wolter and Timlin, 1993, 1998, 2011) from the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, and the Fremantle mean sea level, obtained from the National Oceanography Centre Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, an indicator for the strength of the Leeuwin Current.

4 Discussion and conclusions

In this study, we developed and used an algorithm to detect dense shelf water transport (DSWT) and estimate the associated cross-shelf transport in a 3D numerical ocean model. We found that DSWT consistently occurred on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS) from 2000 until 2023, predominantly during colder months and typically peaking in June at $>60\%$ (consistent with other studies: Mahjabin et al., 2020; van der Mheen et al., 2024). Mean cross-shelf velocities during DSWT events were 0.05 m s^{-1} , with maximum velocities of 0.2 m s^{-1} , which is consistent with previous observations (maximum DSWT velocities of $\sim 0.10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ from a mooring on the WCS; Mahjabin et al., 2019a; Pattiaratchi et al., 2011) and modeling studies on the WCS (daily mean bottom currents $<0.10 \text{ m s}^{-1}$ during DSWT events; Mahjabin et al., 2019b). DSWT had an average thickness of 6 m and a maximum thickness of 27 m, similar to thicknesses of DSWT on Australia’s North West Shelf (Shearman and Brink, 2010). DSWT extended up to an average 40 m and maximum 150 m depth on the shelf, also consistent with previous studies (Mahjabin et al., 2020). DSWT did not occur evenly on the WCS but peaked around $0.8 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ in two “hotspot” locations to the north of Wadjemup. These hotspots are related to local bathymetry and topography as well as the Leeuwin Current (LC; the polewards flowing boundary current on the WCS). One of these hotspot locations was also pointed out by Mahjabin et al. (2019b). Transport values of $0.8 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$ are comparable to those found in other studies globally (0.5 to $1.6 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$; Shapiro et al., 2003) as well as on the North West Shelf ($0.5 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$; Shearman and Brink, 2010).

The algorithm that we developed and used in this study to detect DSWT performed with high accuracy and our results are comparable to other studies. As with similar algorithms it could be further improved (see Methods). The algorithm enables large-scale analyses of DSWT in 3D ocean models, which is an important step forward in understanding cross-shelf transport in coastal oceanography. However, the correct detection of DSWT using the algorithm depends on the ability of the analyzed ocean model to reproduce DSWT. Although several models have been shown to simulate DSWT (e.g. Janekovic et al., 2014; Mihanovic et al., 2018; Mahjabin et al., 2019b; Luneva et al., 2020), ocean models are generally optimized to simulate along-shore ocean currents and may simulate cross-shelf transport less reliably. We determined cross-shelf transport values associated with DSWT, yet other processes may also affect these cross-shelf velocities (including along-shore boundary currents such as the LC). Since it is extremely challenging to separate these different effects (e.g. Brink, 2016), determining cross-shelf transport associated with (rather than caused purely by) DSWT is nevertheless an advancement.

Both DSWT occurrence and associated cross-shelf transport on the WCS were highly correlated with the inshore surface buoyancy flux, which on the WCS is predominantly driven by the ocean surface heat flux. Conditions other than the inshore surface buoyancy flux are important for DSWT: a negative horizontal density gradient (higher density along the coast) is a prerequisite for DSWT to form, but this condition is mostly met during colder months on the WCS (e.g. van der Mheen et al., 2024); and wind mixing can disrupt DSWT formation and events, especially on timescales of several days (e.g. Mahjabin et al., 2019a,b). However, given the strong correlation we found here, the inshore surface buoyancy flux seems the main driver and predictor of DSWT on the WCS. In the Nordic Seas, surface buoyancy fluxes have previously also been found to predict dense water formation and export to first order (Isachsen et al., 2007). In contrast, in the Adriatic Sea, “preconditioning” phases, predominantly related to freshwater river influxes, are critical to dense water formation (Janekovic et al., 2014) and cannot be predicted using instantaneous surface buoyancy fluxes alone (e.g. Vilibic, 2003; Mihanovic et al., 2018).

The strong correlation between surface buoyancy fluxes and DSWT we found here, implies that 1D water column models may be sufficient to predict the formation of DSWT. Although we confirmed this strong correlation for the WCS only, buoyancy fluxes are the primary forcing mechanism of DSWT in several other locations around Australia (Mahjabin et al., 2020), so the strong correlation may hold across much of the Australian continental shelf. This opens possibilities not only for the prediction of DSWT but also for the more ambitious goal of determining simple parametrizations of associated cross-shelf transport (Brink, 2016), for example for use in global ocean biogeochemical models.

Although DSWT occurred consistently on the WCS from 2000 to 2023, there was strong interannual variability in both DSWT occurrence (relative yearly anomalies $\sim 25\%$) and associated cross-shelf transport (relative yearly anomalies up to 50%). This variability was related to the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO; e.g. Wolter and Timlin 2011), with DSWT occurrence and cross-shelf transport increasing during La Niña years. During these years, the polewards flowing LC increases in strength (Pattiaratchi and Buchan, 1991; Feng et al., 2003, 2009; Wijeratne et al., 2018; Bitencourt et al., 2024), resulting in warmer and lower salinity water offshore. There were also stronger negative buoyancy fluxes at the ocean surface along the coast during these years. These effects were particularly pronounced during the strong La Niña in 2011, during which an unseasonably strong LC resulted in a marine heatwave along Western Australia (Feng et al., 2013) and DSWT occurred on the WCS even during the warmer months (when DSWT is usually absent). We suggest that this was related both to increased negative buoyancy fluxes along the coast, and to lower than normal density water offshore (warmer and lower salinity related to the stronger LC) resulting in an unseasonal negative horizontal density gradient. Since 2015 was the only strong and

year-round El Niño event in our dataset, we could not determine the effect of El Niño on DSWT. However, years with a weaker than normal LC were typically associated with less DSWT occurrence and cross-shelf transport. This was particularly evident during the “hiatus” of the LC (2002-2008; Kolbusz et al., 2022). Although not all interannual variability in DSWT on the WCS could be explained by ENSO, we were unable to determine a clear effect of other climate modes.

The response of ENSO to anthropogenic warming is far from resolved (Cai et al., 2021), but (perhaps still somewhat controversially) El Niño events are predicted to increase in the next decade as a result of astronomical forcing (Valle-Levinson, 2024), with a corresponding decrease in the strength of the LC (Valle-Levinson and Pattiaratchi, 2024). If these predictions are accurate, it could imply that DSWT and associated cross-shelf exchange on the WCS may weaken in the upcoming decade.

Although DSWT extended to relatively shallow depths on the WCS, it still results in substantial cross-shelf exchange, with a mean cross-shelf transport across the 50 m bathymetry contour of $0.02 \text{ m}^2\text{s}^{-1}$, which would amount to 0.68 Sv ($1 \text{ Sv} = 10^6 \text{ m}^3\text{s}^{-1}$) over the entire Australian continental shelf (assuming that similar transport values are valid across Australia’s 28000 km long continental shelf). In comparison, Shapiro et al. (2003) estimated a total global cross-shelf DSWT of 3 Sv and more recently Luneva et al. (2020) estimated transport values of 1.3 Sv in the Arctic. This implies that DSWT along Australia may contribute substantially to global cross-shelf exchange.

Most studies of dense water formation and transport focus mainly on the polar regions (e.g. Baines and Condie, 1998; Luneva et al., 2020; Li et al., 2023) or on extreme events where dense water reaches depths $>1000 \text{ m}$ (e.g. Canals et al., 2006; de Madron et al., 2013). However, this study highlights that less deep and less extreme occurrences of DSWT are relevant for cross-shelf exchange. In the Gulf of Lion in the Mediterranean Sea, DSWT reaching depths shallower than 500 m also occurs regularly (Fos-Serdà, 2023). It is likely that similar transport occurs along continental shelves in many other locations around the world as well, particularly mid-latitude continental shelves with Mediterranean climates. Given that DSWT is typically associated with the export of oxygenated, carbon-enriched coastal waters to the deeper open ocean, it may play a key role in the global carbon cycle (e.g. Tsugonai et al., 1999; Thomas et al., 2004; Holt et al., 2009; Dai et al., 2022), as well as potentially mitigate deoxygenation effects caused by anthropogenic warming (e.g. Keeling et al., 2010; Gong et al., 2021). As such, DSWT may be a globally overlooked phenomenon on mid-latitude continental shelves contributing to cross-shelf transport and vital biogeochemical cycles and marine ecosystem dynamics.

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Data Availability Statement

Our (Python) code to detect dense shelf water transport is available through https://github.com/mheen/dswt_detector. CWA-ROMS data is freely available and can be requested through the corresponding author MvdM. Multivariate ENSO Index v2 values are available through the National and Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) and were downloaded from <https://psl.noaa.gov/enso/mei/>. Fremantle mean sea level data can be obtained from the National Oceanography Centre Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level at <https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/111.php>. ERA-5 wind data was obtained through the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF). Ocean glider data for example transects were obtained from Australia's Integrated Marine Observing System (IMOS), which is enabled by the National Collaborative Research Infrastructure Strategy (NCRIS). Data was downloaded from the Australian Ocean Data Network (AODN): <https://portal.aodn.org.au/>.

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Supporting Material for

Resolving the importance of dense shelf water transport for cross-shelf exchange

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This supporting information provides additional figures:

Supporting Methods

- S1 Example scenario where the vertical density gradient $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ exceeded the condition $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at the ocean surface, which is the motivation to limit our dense shelf water transport (DSWT) detection algorithm to the bottom 30% of grid cells in the numerical ocean model.
- S2 Performance test results of the DSWT detection algorithm compared to manual detection.
- S3 Performance compared to suitable conditions for DSWT on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf as determined by van der Mheen et al. (2024).
- S4 Comparison of cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT as calculated by the algorithm and in several CWA-ROMS bottom layers both during DSWT and overall.
- S5 Example scenario where DSWT was falsely detected by our algorithm. In this scenario, negative (onshore) cross-shelf transport of dense water protruding up the shelf from deeper water was wrongly detected. We excluded these detections by removing negative cross-shelf transport values from our results.
- S6 Example scenario where DSWT was falsely detected by our algorithm. In this scenario, dense water cascading off the shelf that was not formed along the coastline (and so does not qualify as dense shelf water transport) was detected. We excluded these detections by removing cross-shelf transport that only started to occur beyond 45 m depth.
- S7 Example scenario where DSWT was falsely detected by our algorithm. In this scenario, DSWT was detected only in transects west of Wadjemup (which start at 40 m depth). Because these transects start in relatively deep water, the condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} < 0$ is sometimes falsely satisfied. We excluded these detections by removing any cross-shelf transport that only occurred in transects off of Wadjemup, but when there was no dense shelf water transport detected in any other transects.
- S8 Example illustrating how we defined DSWT “events”.

Supporting Results

- S9 Yearly mean statistics of DSWT events.
- S10 Interannual variability of wind forcing and potential energy anomaly (as a measure of stratification) on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf.
- S11 Interannual variability of buoyancy forcing inshore on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf.
- S12 Interannual variability of buoyancy forcing offshore on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf.
- S13 DSWT occurrence and cross-shelf transport during the 2011 La Niña and bi-monthly mean sea surface temperature maps.
- S14 As above but showing bi-monthly mean cross-shelf transport maps associated with DSWT.
- S15 DSWT occurrence and cross-shelf transport during the 2022 La Niña and bi-monthly mean sea surface temperature maps.
- S16 As above but showing bi-monthly mean cross-shelf transport maps associated with DSWT.

Supporting Methods

Figure S1 : Example scenario where the vertical density gradient $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z}$ exceeded the condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$ at the ocean surface as a result of high sea surface salinity. To prevent similar scenarios from being detected as a dense shelf water transport event, we included the condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$ in the bottom 30% of grid cells in our detection algorithm. Water properties along an example transect in CWA-ROMS on the 15th of January 2017. The water (a) temperature, (b) salinity, (c) density, and (d) vertical density gradient along the transect shown by the red line in the inset map in panel a.

Figure S2 : Performance of the dense shelf water transport (DSWT) detection algorithm in determining whether DSWT occurs in a transect in comparison to a manual determination based on plots of water density, temperature and salinity along a transect (see Methods in the main manuscript). Tests were done for 2017, which is considered a neutral El Niño Southern Oscillation year. (a) Number of transects for which a manual comparison was done per month. The largest number of comparisons were done during months in which DSWT most commonly occurs on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf. (b) Number of disagreements per month between a manual determination of DSWT and that of the algorithm. False negatives by the algorithm are shown in blue and false positives in red. A total of 1030 transects were compared. The algorithm had an accuracy of 91.7%. Of the wrongly identified DSWT cases, 46.5% were false positives and 53.5% were false negatives.

Figure S3 : Performance of dense shelf water transport (DSWT) detection algorithm on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS) in 2017 compared to the percentage of suitable conditions for DSWT formation determined by van der Mheen et al. (2024). (a) Monthly suitable conditions for DSWT on the WCS by van der Mheen et al. (2024). (b) DSWT occurrence on the WCS as detected by the algorithm.

Figure S4 : Cross-shelf transport comparisons across the 50 m bathymetry contour during 2017. (a) Cross-shelf transport associated with dense shelf water transport (DSWT) as calculated by the algorithm in down-transect directions (green bars) and from different bottom layers in CWA-ROMS, calculated perpendicular to the 50 m contour (black markers). Cross-shelf transport calculated by the algorithm agrees well with transport in the bottom 3 layers of CWA-ROMS. (b) Overall cross-shelf transport across the 50 m contour in the bottom 3 layers of CWA-ROMS (black circles) compared to the transport associated with DSWT (green bars, as in panel a).

01-01-2017 00:00 - DSWT wrongly detected

Figure S5 : Example scenario where dense shelf water transport (DSWT) was wrongly detected by our algorithm and negative (towards the coast) cross-shelf transport was found. The first condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} < 0$ was satisfied due to the more saline, higher density water along the coast. Cold bottom water flowing up the shelf around 40 to 50 m depth (panel a and e) exceeded the second condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$, which led to the detection of negative DSWT transport (indicated by the red boxes in panel d) in this scenario. We excluded these faulty detections by ignoring any negative cross-shelf transport in our results. Water properties along an example transect in CWA-ROMS on the 1st of January 2017. The water (a) temperature, (b) salinity, (c) density, and (d) vertical density gradient along the transect shown by the red line in the inset map in panel a. Maps of the (e) bottom and (f) surface temperature from CWA-ROMS, with black arrows indicating ocean current velocities. The black line in both panels indicates the example transect shown in panels a-d. The light grey arrow in panel f indicates the daily mean wind speed and direction at the transect location.

09-02-2017 03:00 - DSWT wrongly detected

Figure S6 : Example scenario where dense shelf water transport (DSWT) was wrongly detected by our algorithm and dense water cascading off the shelf was found (rather than dense water forming along the coast and then being transported along the seafloor towards the continental shelf edge). The first condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} < 0$ was satisfied due to the more saline, higher density water along the coast. Cold bottom water flowing off the shelf around 50 to 100 m depth (panel a and e) exceeded the second condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial z} > 0.02 \text{ kg m}^{-3} \text{ m}^{-1}$, which led to the detection of DSWT transport in deeper layers (indicated by the red boxes in panel d) in this scenario. We excluded these faulty detections by ignoring any cases where transport associated with DSWT only occurs deeper than 45 m along a transect. Water properties along an example transect in CWA-ROMS on the 9th of February 2017. The water (a) temperature, (b) salinity, (c) density, and (d) vertical density gradient along the transect shown by the red line in the inset map in panel a. Maps of the (e) bottom and (f) surface temperature from CWA-ROMS, with black arrows indicating ocean current velocities. The black line in both panels indicates the example transect shown in panels a-d. The light grey arrow in panel f indicates the daily mean wind speed and direction at the transect location.

11-02-2017 21:00 - DSWT wrongly detected

Figure S7 : Example scenario where dense shelf water transport (DSWT) was wrongly detected only in transects off of Wadjemup (Rottneest Island). These transects were manually added starting from the 40 m bathymetry contour, because automatically generated transects from the 10 m bathymetry contour resulted in transects crossing others (see also Methods in the main manuscript). Because these transects start in relatively deep water, the first condition that $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} < 0$ is sometimes wrongly satisfied. Although in this scenario there is colder, denser water flowing offshore along the seafloor (panels a, c, d) this is not related to DSWT, where we expect cold water to form along the coast (no band of colder water along the coast in panels e and f). We excluded these faulty detections by ignoring any transport in the transects off Wadjemup if these are the only transects where DSWT was detected. Water properties along an example transect in CWA-ROMS on the 11th of February 2017. The water (a) temperature, (b) salinity, (c) density, and (d) vertical density gradient along the transect shown by the red line in the inset map in panel a. Maps of the (e) bottom and (f) surface temperature from CWA-ROMS, with black arrows indicating ocean current velocities. The black line in both panels indicates the example transect shown in panels a-d. The light grey arrow in panel f indicates the daily mean wind speed and direction at the transect location.

Figure S8 : Example demonstrating how we define dense shelf water transport (DSWT) “events” in the main manuscript (see Methods). Daily DSWT occurrence percentage on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS) for 2017 (blue line). We define peaks above 20% (red crosses) in DSWT occurrence as an “event”. The duration of each event is determined as the time at which the occurrence percentage first starts to rise towards a peak until the time at which it first stops falling after a peak. Although this is a simplified definition, it gives an initial indication of how often DSWT starts to form and is disrupted (for example by mixing due to wind) on the WCS as well as how long these cycles of formation and disruption typically take.

Supporting Results

Figure S9 : Yearly mean statistics of dense shelf water transport (DSWT) events (see Methods in the main manuscript and Figure S8 for the definition of an “event”). **(a)** Number of DSWT events per year. **(b)** Mean duration of DSWT events. **(c)** Mean cross-shelf velocity (directed away from the coastal ocean) during DSWT events. **(d)** Mean thickness of water layer in which DSWT events occur. **(e)** Mean depth contour along the shelf reached by DSWT events. In panels c-e the green bars indicate the yearly mean over all events and the black crosses the yearly mean of the maximum value of each event.

Figure S10 : Interannual variability of wind forcing and stratification on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS). (a) Monthly El Niño Southern Oscillation indicator, using the Multivariate ENSO Index v2 obtained from the National and Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) at <https://ps1.noaa.gov/enso/mei/>. Monthly Fremantle mean sea level anomaly, which is an indicator for the strength of the Leeuwin Current on the WCS. Data obtained from the National Oceanography Centre Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level at <https://psmsl.org/data/obtaining/stations/111.php>. (b) Monthly wind speed anomalies and wind directions on the WCS from the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF) ERA-5 model. (c) Potential energy anomaly (PEA) anomaly on the WCS as a measure of stratification. PEA was calculated over depths up to 50 m on the WCS based on water densities from CWA-ROMS (see Methods in the main manuscript). Negative PEA anomalies suggest less stratification than usual, which may prohibit the formation of dense shelf water transport.

Figure S11 : Interannual variability of buoyancy forcing inshore on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS). **(a)** Monthly El niño Southern Oscillation indicator and Fremantle mean sea level anomaly, as in Figure S10 a. **(b)** Inshore (depths up to 30 m, as indicated by the blue shaded area in the inset map) surface heat flux anomaly and sea surface temperature anomaly from CWA-ROMS (see Methods in the main manuscript). **(c)** Inshore surface salt flux anomaly and sea surface salinity from CWA-ROMS. **(d)** Resulting inshore buoyancy flux anomaly.

Figure S12 : Interannual variability buoyancy forcing on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf as in Figure S11 but for further offshore regions (depths between 50 to 300 m, as indicated by the red shaded area in the inset map in panel b).

2011 La Nina

Figure S13 : Dense shelf water transport (DSWT) on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS) for 2011 (La Niña year). **(a)** Monthly mean occurrence of DSWT over all transects. **(b)** Monthly mean cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT across the 50 m bathymetry contour. **(c)** Monthly sea surface temperature (SST) gradient anomaly, calculated as the difference between average SST up to 30 m depth and SST in water between 50 and 300 m depth on the WCS. A negative anomaly indicates a larger than normal negative temperature gradient, which is associated with more DSWT. Mean sea surface temperature maps for **(d)** December and January, **(e)** February and March, **(f)** April and May, **(g)** June and July, **(h)** August and September, **(i)** October and November.

2011 La Nina

Figure S14 : **(a-c)** As in Figure S13 . Mean DSWT cross-shelf transport maps up to 100 m depth for **(d)** December and January, **(e)** February and March, **(f)** April and May, **(g)** June and July, **(h)** August and September, **(i)** October and November.

2022 La Nina

Figure S15 : Dense shelf water transport (DSWT) on the Wadjemup Continental Shelf (WCS) for 2022 (La Niña year). **(a)** Monthly mean occurrence of DSWT over all transects. **(b)** Monthly mean cross-shelf transport associated with DSWT across the 50 m bathymetry contour. **(c)** Monthly sea surface temperature (SST) gradient anomaly, calculated as the difference between average SST up to 30 m depth and SST in water between 50 and 300 m depth on the WCS. A negative anomaly indicates a larger than normal negative temperature gradient, which is associated with more DSWT. Mean sea surface temperature maps for **(d)** December and January, **(e)** February and March, **(f)** April and May, **(g)** June and July, **(h)** August and September, **(i)** October and November.

2022 La Nina

Figure S16 : **(a-c)** As in Figure S15 . Mean DSWT cross-shelf transport maps up to 100 m depth for **(d)** December and January, **(e)** February and March, **(f)** April and May, **(g)** June and July, **(h)** August and September, **(i)** October and November.